

**AWARENESS AND SATISFACTION OF THE REGISTERED BOOKKEEPERS ON
THE ONLINE REGISTRATION AND UPDATE SYSTEM (ORUS) OF
THE BUREAU OF INTERNAL REVENUE**

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Awareness and Satisfaction of the Registered Bookkeepers on the Online Registration and Update System (ORUS) of the Bureau of Internal Revenue

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Abstract

The Online Registration and Update System (ORUS) is developed by the Bureau of Internal Revenue as part of its digitalization of operations. It is to primarily enable taxpayers to register, update, and transact registration-related transactions online. The study entitled, "Awareness and Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS of the Bureau of Internal Revenue" aimed to determine the level of awareness and satisfaction along its relationship among identified variables. A descriptive method was used with 146 respondents who were registered bookkeepers of Revenue District 78 Binalbagan as of December 2022. A questionnaire that underwent validity and reliability was used to assess bookkeeper's awareness and satisfaction, and summarized the results in tables. Findings revealed that the respondents comprised of more 23 and 30 years old, female, and with 1-5 years in practice. It also showed that the Registered bookkeepers are highly aware of the ORUS. Those who are 23 - 30 years old are highly aware of the ORUS with a mean score of 3.75, male registered bookkeepers manifest a mean score of 3.70, interpreted also as highly aware and respondents who have 11 - 15 years of practice has the highest mean score of 3.69 interpreted as highly aware. In terms of age, registered bookkeepers are highly satisfied on the ORUS having the 63 - 70 years old who displayed the highest mean score of 3.77. Male respondents show the highest mean score of 3.65 interpreted as highly satisfied and those who have been in the practice for 11 - 15 years of practice shows the highest mean of 3.64 interpreted as highly satisfied. There were no significant differences in the awareness of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped according to their age, sex, and years of practice. It is presented in the computed values of 6.00, 2109.50, and 1.27 and p-values of 0.306, 0.740, and 0.737, respectively. There were no significant differences in the satisfaction of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped according to their age, sex, and years of practice as shown in the computed values of 4.07, 2177.50, and 0.831 and p-values of 0.539, 0.997, and 0.842, respectively.

Keywords: awareness, satisfaction, Registered Bookkeepers, Online Registration and Update System (ORUS), Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR)

Introduction

Taxes are the lifeblood of any country. Without them, the government cannot run. It is essential to reiterate the value of taxes because they contribute to the formation of a country. By paying taxes, we people contribute in some way to the success of these initiatives by enabling the government to develop new social programs and plans (Malicdem, Vigo & Abante, 2023). The Bureau of Internal Revenue (BIR) has realized that it must innovate to keep up with the rapid technological advancement to guarantee that it gets its fair share of taxes from the digital economy. The "BIR Digital Transformation (DX) Roadmap 2020-2030" or Revenue Memorandum Order (RMO) No. 27-2020 is one such measure that complies with Republic Act (RA) No. 11032, also known as the "Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018". One of the main objectives of the BIR's Digital Transformation Plan for 2022–2023 is to make registration easy, accessible, and quick for all taxpayers. In order to facilitate online registration-related operations, the BIR has introduced the Online Registration and Update System (ORUS), which enables taxpayers to register, update, and transact with the BIR.

Revenue Memorandum Circular (RMC) No. 153-2022 states that the ORUS is a web-based system that offers a straightforward and substitute option for all taxpayers to complete their registration with the tax authorities from beginning to end. This circular was released on December 12, 2022. The system enhances the BIR collections as it moves towards a long-overdue digital journey. Its objective is to enable taxpayers to register, update, and carry out transactions about registration from the convenience of their homes over the Internet. The technological development has various effects on citizens' daily lives, among which is the growing importance of e-governance. An e-government website is an essential communication platform that supports government-citizen interaction.

Awareness and satisfaction are components of an ongoing improvement process. The agency needs to prioritize strategies to ensure that bookkeepers are well-informed about the system and satisfied with their experience using it. Through consistent feedback monitoring and insight-driven change implementation, the bureau can adjust to the changing needs of taxpayers, regulatory requirements, and technology improvements.

By 2028, the BIR aspire that all transactions will be done digitally which means manual transaction will not be practiced anymore. However, there are still bookkeepers who were not aware of the existence of the digital transactions since its implementation.

Therefore, this study aimed to gather bookkeepers' perspectives on the ORUS of the BIR. Specifically, it sought to determine bookkeepers' awareness and satisfaction with how this new system drove them to adopt and use the revenue application.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to determine the awareness and satisfaction of the Registered Bookkeepers on the Online registration and Update System (ORUS) of the Bureau of Internal Revenue. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. number of years in practice?
2. What is the level of awareness of registered bookkeepers when taken as a whole and in terms of:
 - 2.1. age;
 - 2.2. sex; and
 - 2.3. years in practice?
3. What is the level of satisfaction of registered bookkeepers when taken as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. age;
 - 3.2. sex; and
 - 3.3. years in practice?
4. Is there a significant difference in the awareness of the use of ORUS when respondents are grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant difference in the satisfaction with the use of ORUS when respondents are grouped according to profile?

Literature Review

The study conducted by Palaco et al. (2019) noted that awareness plays an essential part in the development of knowledge and information about a system. People use the systems on their level of awareness.

Furthermore, the study of Pargmann, Riebenbauer, & Berding (2023) stated that the digitalization of processes in accounting required graduates to upskill themselves to learn digitalization in various areas of accounting. The results of the study revealed that in terms of the awareness of the respondents, it is evident that most of them are not aware and lacks the expertise in the use of technology that enables employees to successfully manage their workplace.

In the study of Shuib, Yadegaridehkordi & Ainin (2019), he stated that taxpayer satisfaction is critical for building trust in the government. The expectations of citizens and end users of government services represent their view of the system's quality. By fostering satisfaction through transparency, efficiency, and responsive service, governments can enhance compliance, increase revenue, improve public services, and promote economic and social well-being. A tax system that is simple to understand and navigate promotes satisfaction. When taxpayers are satisfied with the tax system, they are more inclined to voluntarily comply. This voluntary cooperation builds trust in the system while reducing conflicting behaviors. Building and maintaining taxpayer satisfaction contributes to a trustworthy relationship between residents and the government, which is critical for a functional tax system and overall public governance.

Moreover, the study by Nhan et al. (2023) aimed to determine the satisfaction of accountants in the use of Accounting Information System. The results of their study revealed that accountants are highly satisfied with digital technology and this satisfaction is mainly influenced by various factors such as the quality of the system, its usefulness, and the information quality. Moreover, it was also revealed that the higher the satisfaction of the accountants are, the higher is their work efficiency. The results of the study also revealed that their knowledge or awareness in using the website also impacted their level of satisfaction on the technology systems.

Diehl et al. (2021) conducted a study on self-perceptions and awareness of aging. According to them, age is subjective, thus adults experience their aging in a diverse way. As people get older, they adjust by focusing on their strengths and finding strategies to compensate for losses. This adaptive technique can alter how people see aging, either positively or negatively. The variety of ways adults experience aging emphasizes the need of taking individual differences and the intricate interplay of circumstances into account when shaping perceptions of age. Recognizing that age is subjective enables a more nuanced view of the aging process.

On sex and technology utilization, the result of the study by Schmidhuber et al. (2020) showed that males assess the perceived utility of new technology's performance-related features more highly than women. It makes clear that, compared to female users, male users thought technology was more beneficial. Awareness can be influenced by how useful a technology is seen to be in one's daily life. If a new technology is more closely related to certain interests or professional tasks, either gender may be more likely to engage with it in greater depth. In some societies, men are expected to lead the way in adopting new technology, whilst women are encouraged to use it for communication or social purposes. These cultural expectations can influence how technology is accepted and the perceived roles of each gender in technological adoption.

Furthermore, Awang et al. (2022) spearheaded a study on different perspective or awareness concerning the use of digital technology may have according to their genders. Through examining the effect of gender to the perception or awareness of accountants, the results of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between the two variables.

However, the findings of this study negate the study by Alderman (2021) which revealed that in terms of gender, it was found that there was a difference between men and women accountants and their ability to use digital technology. The results of the study revealed that in terms of gender, women in accounting are on a higher risk of job displacement in the Smart Machine Age highlighting the need for women to be supported to pursue advancement in technological literacy.

The findings of the study made by Mohd Faizal et al. (2022) presented that as long as it can help them to perform well in their job, professionals were eager to learn about any digital technology. It implies that keeping up with technology changes is more about ongoing learning and adaptation than merely having years of expertise. As a result, both novice and seasoned practitioners can achieve comparable levels of awareness in circumstances that promote continual professional development and equal access to knowledge.

The research conducted by Lardizabal et al. (2023) found no connection between demographics like age. Because of the richness of the human experience, age alone is unable to fully describe the highly individualized and broad conditions that are satisfaction. Satisfaction is a multidimensional feeling influenced by a number of aspects that go far beyond chronological age. Satisfaction levels can fluctuate during a person's life as a result of life events, changes in circumstances, and shifting personal aspirations. These changes imply that contentment at any particular age is impacted by a complicated set of factors other than age itself. Understanding satisfaction requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account the complicated and changing character of each individual's life circumstances, rather than using age as a descriptor.

Schmidhuber et al. (2020) found out in their study that men are more likely than women to have access to and be proficient in using technology, which can lead to feelings of contentment and success. It frequently reflects disparities in how each gender interacts with technology, assesses its value, and encounters hurdles to use because when technology aligns with their expectations, it increases their overall satisfaction.

Mohd Faizal et al. (2022) posited that as long as it enables them to work with greater efficiency, flexibility, and control every day and if they feel they are getting good value, satisfaction tends to be higher. It displays the technology's ability to meet a wide range of user needs. This suggests that the technology is well-designed to serve users at all phases of their professional path, ensuring that everyone benefits from its features.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive research design was used in this study to describe the profile of bookkeepers and to demonstrate the association or relationship between awareness and satisfaction. This descriptive study answers questions concerning the awareness and satisfaction of bookkeepers. According to McCombes (2022), this method of research focuses on accurately and systematically describing a population, situation, or phenomenon.

Respondents

A purposive sampling technique was used in this study. All of the 146 registered bookkeepers of Revenue District 78 Binalbagan, Negros Occidental, who were registered as of December 2022, were the study's subject and respondents.

Instrument

Without standardized instruments, the proponents employed a questionnaire that underwent a content validity and reliability tests that were inspired by the study of De Castro et al. (2015). The questionnaire or survey instrument was revised and fine-tuned with the assistance of field experts. It was to ensure that the data collected was accurate, consistent, and relevant to the research objectives, thereby enhancing the quality and credibility of the research findings and supporting informed decision-making across different disciplines and applications. The overall mean score of the three expert validators was 4.18 and the reliability index was 0.949

The questionnaire was composed of two sections: the Respondent Profile was in the first section, and the Bookkeepers' Level of Awareness and Satisfaction was provided in the second. The profile of the respondents, including age, sex, and years in practice, is covered in Part I of the questionnaire; Part II of the questionnaire assessed the level of awareness and satisfaction of the respondents about the Online Registration and Update System (ORUS) of BIR.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher secured a letter addressed to the Revenue District Officer of Revenue District 78 Binalbagan to know the actual number of registered bookkeepers and from the President of the bookkeeper's association in Revenue District 78 Binalbagan subject for approval to conduct the survey. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires through the assistance of co-employees and collection agents. Questionnaires were distributed to all the bookkeepers.

The researcher gathered the questionnaire as soon as the respondents completed it. The data were collected to help the researchers determine the level of awareness and satisfaction of the respondents. The completed answer sheets were collected right away and were statistically analyzed.

Data Analysis

To respond to statement of the problem 1 statement which states, what is the profile of bookkeepers in terms of age, sex, and number of years in service, frequency, and percentage distribution were used. The mean was used to answer the statement of the problem 2 and 3 which states, what is the level of awareness of registered bookkeepers in terms of age, sex, and years in service, and what is the level of satisfaction of registered bookkeepers when grouped according to age, sex, and years in service. To answer the statement of the problem 4 and 5 which states, is there a significant difference in the awareness on the use of ORUS when respondents are grouped according to profile, and is there a significant difference in the satisfaction on the use of ORUS when respondents are grouped according to profile, Kruskal Wallis H-Test was used when grouped according to age and number of years in practice and Mann-Whitney (U) Test in terms of sex.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that respondent privacy and confidentiality came first. Only the thesis adviser and researcher have access to individual survey data. Additionally, the names of the respondents were purposefully left out of the final report in order to preserve anonymity. This methodical approach demonstrates the dedication to ethical research procedures and respondents' confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

Profile of Bookkeepers

There were 146 respondents in this study. A list of registered bookkeepers broken down by age, sex, and years of experience is provided below.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of Registered Bookkeepers in Terms of Age, Sex, and Years in Practice*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	23 - 30 years old	45	30.80
	31 - 38 years old	38	26.00
	39 - 46 years old	30	20.50
	47 - 54 years old	21	14.40
	55 - 62 years old	6	4.10
	63 - 70 years old	6	4.10
	Total	146	100
Sex	Male	42	28.80
	Female	104	71.20
	Total	146	100.00
Number of Years in Practice	1 - 5 years	84	57.50
	6 - 10 years	41	28.10
	11 - 15 years	18	12.30
	16 - 20 years	3	2.10
	Total	146	100.00

Table 1 shows that as to age, 45 (30.80%) of the bookkeepers were of 23 - 30 years old, 38 (26.00%) of them are 31 - 38 years old, 30 (20.50%) are 39 - 46 years old, 21 (14.40%) are 47 - 54 years old, 55 - 62 years and 63 - 70 years old have a frequency of six (4.10%), respectively.

In terms of sex, 104 (71.20%) of the respondents are female and 42 (28.80%) are male.

As to years in practice, 84 (57.50%) of the respondents are practicing for 1-5 years, 41 (28.10%) of them have 6 -10 years in practice, 18 (12.30) have 11 - 15 years in practice, and three (2.10%) are in 16 - 20 years of practice.

The table shows that most of the bookkeepers are of age 23-30 years old, female, and almost half of the subject respondents are newly registered with 1 - 5 years of experience.

Level of Awareness of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped According to Profile

The data on level of awareness on the ORUS according to age, sex, and years in practice are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2 shows that in terms of age, on average, all bookkeepers are highly aware of ORUS of the BIR. Respondents of ages 23-30 years old have a mean of 3.75, 31-38 years old respondents have a mean of 3.72, 39-46 years old display a mean of 3.62, 47-54 years old show a mean of 3.51, 55-62 years old presents a mean of 3.64, and 63-70 years old have a mean of 3.73.

As to sex, males and females show high level of awareness of the ORUS with a mean of 3.70 and 3.67. Also, when it comes to the number of years in practice, bookkeepers are highly aware with 1-5 years in practice displaying a mean of 3.69, 6-10 years have a mean

of 3.67, 11-15 years shows a mean of 3.69, and 16-20 years display a mean of 3.33. As a whole, the mean score of the registered bookkeepers is 3.68 interpreted as highly aware.

Table 2. *Level of Awareness of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Profile*

Profile	Category	f	Mean	Interpretation
Age	23 - 30 years old	45	3.75	Highly Aware
	31 - 38 years old	38	3.72	Highly Aware
	39 - 46 years old	30	3.62	Highly Aware
	47 - 54 years old	21	3.51	Highly Aware
	55 - 62 years old	6	3.64	Highly Aware
	63 - 70 years old	6	3.73	Highly Aware
Sex	Male	42	3.70	Highly Aware
	Female	104	3.67	Highly Aware
Number of Years in Practice	1 - 5 years	84	3.69	Highly Aware
	6 - 10 years	41	3.67	Highly Aware
	11 - 15 years	18	3.69	Highly Aware
	16 - 20 years	3	3.33	Highly Aware
As a Whole		146	3.68	Highly Aware

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Highly Aware; 2.51 - 3.25, Aware; 1.76 - 2.50, Less Aware; 1.00 - 1.75, Not Aware

The findings revealed that the registered bookkeepers are informed about the ORUS by the Bureau of Internal Revenue District 78. Ensuring awareness between males and females as it promotes equal opportunity in accessing and utilizing the system and the outcomes demonstrated that the registered bookkeepers of Revenue District 78 can adapt quickly to changes, ensuring to remain relevant and competitive in their field.

The result of this study conforms to the study of Palaco et al. (2019) which noted that awareness plays an essential part in the development of knowledge and information about a system. People use the systems on their level of awareness.

It also confirms to the study of Pargmann et al. (2023) which stated that the digitalization of processes in accounting required graduates to upskill themselves to learn digitalization in various areas of accounting. The results of the study revealed that in terms of the awareness of the respondents, it is evident that most of them are not aware and lacks the expertise in the use of technology that enables employees to successfully manage their workplace.

Level of Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Age, Sex, and Years in Practice

Table 3 exhibits the data concerning the level of satisfaction on the ORUS by age, sex, and years in practice.

Table 3. *Level of Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According Age, Sex, and Years in Practice*

Profile	Category	f	Mean	Interpretation
Age	23 - 30 years old	45	3.67	Highly Satisfied
	31 - 38 years old	38	3.68	Highly Satisfied
	39 - 46 years old	30	3.52	Highly Satisfied
	47 - 54 years old	21	3.52	Highly Satisfied
	55 - 62 years old	6	3.50	Highly Satisfied
	63 - 70 years old	6	3.77	Highly Satisfied
Sex	Male	42	3.65	Highly Satisfied
	Female	104	3.60	Highly Satisfied
Number of Years in Practice	1 - 5 years	84	3.63	Highly Satisfied
	6 - 10 years	41	3.58	Highly Satisfied
	11 - 15 years	18	3.64	Highly Satisfied
	16 - 20 years	3	3.42	Highly Satisfied
As a Whole		146	3.62	Highly Satisfied

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Highly Aware; 2.51 - 3.25, Aware; 1.76 - 2.50, Less Aware; 1.00 - 1.75, Not Aware

Table 3 shows the high level of satisfaction on the ORUS that all registered bookkeepers, regardless of age (M=3.67, M=3.68, M=3.52, M=3.52, M=3.50, and M=3.77) have with the ORUS.

Results provide information that both males (M=3.65) and females (M=3.60) are highly satisfied with the ORUS of the Bureau of Internal Revenue. Despite years of practice in their chosen field, outcomes indicated that the registered bookkeepers in Revenue District 78 are highly satisfied (M=3.63, M=3.58, M=3.64, and M=3.42) with the features and benefits that the new system offers thus promoting faster adoption. As a whole, all of the registered bookkeepers are highly satisfied on the ORUS (M=3.62).

The finding of this study is in consonance with the statement of Shuib, Yadegaridehkordi, & Ainin (2019). According to him, taxpayer satisfaction is critical for building trust in the government. The expectations of citizens and end users of government services represent their view of the system's quality. By fostering satisfaction through transparency, efficiency, and responsive service, governments can enhance compliance, increase revenue, improve public services, and promote economic and social well-being. A tax system that is simple to understand and navigate promotes satisfaction. When taxpayers are satisfied with the tax system, they are more inclined to voluntarily comply. This voluntary cooperation builds trust in the system while reducing conflicting behaviors. Building and maintaining taxpayer satisfaction contributes to a trustworthy relationship between residents and the government, which is critical for a functional tax system and overall public governance.

Moreover, it is in agreement to the findings of the study by Nhan et al. (2023) which aimed to determine the satisfaction of accountants in the use of Accounting Information System. The results of their study revealed that accountants are highly satisfied with digital technology and this satisfaction is mainly influenced by various factors such as the quality of the system, its usefulness, and the information quality. Moreover, it was also revealed that the higher the satisfaction of the accountants are, the higher is their work efficiency. The results of the study also revealed that their knowledge or awareness in using the website also impacted their level of satisfaction on the technology systems.

Difference in the Awareness of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Age

The table below shows the difference in the awareness of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped according to age.

Table 4.1. *Difference in the Awareness on the ORUS when Grouped According to Age*

Age	n	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
23 - 30 years old	45	79.79	6.00	0.306	Accept Ho
31 - 38 years old	38	77.87			
39 - 46 years old	30	69.27			
47 - 54 years old	21	58.00			
55 - 62 years old	6	60.83			
63 - 70 years old	6	86.75			
Total	146				

The result of the Krustal-Wallis test showed no significant difference in the awareness on the ORUS as to age ($H=6.00$, $p=0.306$) at 0.05 level of significance.

The result implies that registered bookkeepers in Revenue District 78 have almost the same level of awareness on the ORUS regardless of their age. Registered bookkeepers of different ages have a similar level of knowledge and understanding about the system. Whether they're younger or older, they're likely to be equally aware of how to use and access the system

This current study offered the same result as the study of Diehl et al. (2021) on self-perceptions and awareness of aging. According to them, age is subjective, thus adults experience their aging in a diverse way. As people get older, they adjust by focusing on their strengths and finding strategies to compensate for losses. This adaptive technique can alter how people see aging, either positively or negatively. The variety of ways adults experience aging emphasizes the need of taking individual differences and the intricate interplay of circumstances into account when shaping perceptions of age. Recognizing that age is subjective enables a more nuanced view of the aging process.

Difference in the Awareness of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Sex

The purpose of this study was to assess whether there were significant differences in registered bookkeepers' awareness on the ORUS based on their sex.

Table 4.2. *Difference in the Awareness on the ORUS when Grouped According to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean Rank	U	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Male	42	75.27	2109.50	0.740	Accept Ho
Female	104	72.78			
Total	146				

The results of the Mann-Whitney U Test showed that there is no significant difference in the awareness on the ORUS when grouped according to sex ($U=2109.50$, $p=0.740$). Considering its p-value which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The result suggests that male and female Registered Bookkeepers have almost the same levels of awareness on the ORUS. Both genders possess similar understanding and knowledge about how to use the system.

This result contradicts the study by Schmidhuber et al. (2020) show that males assess the perceived utility of new technology's

performance-related features more highly than women. It makes clear that, compared to female users, male users thought technology was more beneficial. Awareness can be influenced by how useful a technology is seen to be in one's daily life. If a new technology is more closely related to certain interests or professional tasks, either gender may be more likely to engage with it in greater depth. In some societies, men are expected to lead the way in adopting new technology, whilst women are encouraged to use it for communication or social purposes. These cultural expectations can influence how technology is accepted and the perceived roles of each gender in technological adoption.

The finding of this study is also closely similar to the statement of Awang et al. (2022) in their study on different perspective or awareness concerning the use of digital technology may have according to their genders. Through examining the effect of gender to the perception or awareness of accountants, the results of the study revealed that there was no significant difference between the two variables.

However, the findings of this study negate the study by Alderman (2021) which revealed that in terms of *gender, it was found that there was a difference between men and women accountants and their ability to use digital technology. The results of the study revealed that in terms of gender, women in accounting are on a higher risk of job displacement in the Smart Machine Age highlighting the need for women to be supported to pursue advancement in technological literacy.

Difference in the Awareness of Registered Bookkeepers According on the ORUS when grouped according to Years in Practice

Difference in the awareness of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped according to years in practice was determined in this study. The data are presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3. *Difference in the Awareness on the ORUS When Grouped According to Years in Practice*

<i>Years in Practice</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
1 - 5 years	84	74.21	1.27	0.737	Accept Ho
6 - 10 years	41	73.63			
11 - 15 years	18	74.28			
16 - 20 years	3	47.17			
Total	146	Total			

The Krustal-Wallis test result revealed that there is no significant difference in awareness on the ORUS according to years of practice ($H=1.27$, $p=0.737$). Since the p-values is higher than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The result shows that regardless of years of practice, registered bookkeepers in Revenue District 78 have about the same degree of awareness on the ORUS. It further means that their experience level doesn't significantly affect their understanding or knowledge of the system. Whether they've been practicing for just a few years or for decades, their awareness of how to use ORUS is generally similar. In simpler terms, both new and veteran bookkeepers are likely to be equally knowledgeable about the ORUS, indicating that the system's information or training might be equally accessible and comprehensible to all.

The findings supported the results made by Mohd Faizal et al. (2022) that as long as it can help them to perform well in their job, professionals were eager to learn about any digital technology. It implies that keeping up with technology changes is more about ongoing learning and adaptation than merely having years of expertise. As a result, both novice and seasoned practitioners can achieve comparable levels of awareness in circumstances that promote continual professional development and equal access to knowledge.

Difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Age

The difference in the satisfaction of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS as expressed in terms of age is presented in Table 5.1 below.

Table 5.1. *The difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Decision @ 0.05</i>
23 - 30 years old	45	77.06	4.07	0.539	Accept Ho
31 - 38 years old	38	78.34			
39 - 46 years old	30	68.37			
47 - 54 years old	21	64.29			
55 - 62 years old	6	58.33			
63 - 70 years old	6	89.25			
Total	146				

The Krustal-Wallis test result revealed that there is no significant difference in the satisfaction on the ORUS in terms of age ($H=4.07$, $p=0.539$) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

This finding implies that the Revenue District 78 registered bookkeepers are satisfied with ORUS regardless of their age. It further

indicates that satisfaction with the system is consistent across different age groups. Both younger and older bookkeepers find the system effective and user-friendly. This also indicates that the ORUS is likely well-designed, intuitive, and accessible, catering to the needs of all users irrespective of their age. This could also imply that the training or resources provided by the BIR are effective in ensuring all age groups understand and can efficiently use the system.

This result of this study is in agreement with research by Lardizabal et al. (2023) which found no connection between demographics like age. Because of the richness of the human experience, age alone is unable to fully describe the highly individualized and broad conditions that are satisfaction. Satisfaction is a multidimensional feeling influenced by a number of aspects that go far beyond chronological age. Satisfaction levels can fluctuate during a person's life as a result of life events, changes in circumstances, and shifting personal aspirations. These changes imply that contentment at any particular age is impacted by a complicated set of factors other than age itself. Understanding satisfaction requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account the complicated and changing character of each individual's life circumstances, rather than using age as a descriptor.

Difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped According to Sex

The difference in the satisfaction of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS when they are grouped as male and female is ascertained in this study. Table 5.2 presents the pertinent data.

Table 5.2. *The difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Sex*

Sex	n	Mean Rank	U	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
Male	42	73.65	2177.50	0.977	Accept Ho
Female	104	73.44			
Total	146				

The results of the Mann-Whitney U Test indicated that there is no significant difference in the satisfaction on the ORUS when grouped according to sex ($U=2177.50$, $p=0.977$). Considering its p-value which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. It implies that the satisfaction on the ORUS of registered bookkeepers who are male and female are approximately equal. Any difference in satisfaction is likely due to random chance rather than a true underlying difference between sexes.

The results are inconsistent with those of the study by Schmidhuber et al. (2020) who found that men are more likely than women to have access to and be proficient in using technology, which can lead to feelings of contentment and success. It frequently reflects disparities in how each gender interacts with technology, assesses its value, and encounters hurdles to use because when technology aligns with their expectations, it increases their overall satisfaction.

Difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when grouped According to Years in Practice

Difference in the satisfaction of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS expressed in terms of years in practice is presented in Table 5.3 below.

Table 5.3. *Difference in the Satisfaction of Registered Bookkeepers on the ORUS when Grouped According to Years in Practice*

Years in Practice	n	Mean Rank	H	P-value	Decision @ 0.05
1 - 5 years	84	73.48	0.83	0.842	Accept Ho
6 - 10 years	41	73.68			
11 - 15 years	18	76.56			
16 - 20 years	3	53.17			
Total	146	Total			

The Krustal-Wallis test result revealed that there is no significant difference in satisfaction of registered bookkeepers on the ORUS expressed in terms of years of practice ($H=0.83$, $p=0.842$). Since the p-values is higher than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The result indicates that regardless of years in practice, registered bookkeepers in Revenue District 78 have about the same degree of satisfaction on the ORUS. This also suggests that the system is effectively meeting the needs of both new and experienced professionals. ORUS was well-designed and user-friendly enough to cater to a wide range of users, from novices to veterans in the field.

This finding is supported by results of the study made by Mohd Faizal et al. (2022) that as long as it enables them to work with greater efficiency, flexibility, and control every day and if they feel they are getting good value, satisfaction tends to be higher. It displays the technology's ability to meet a wide range of user needs. This suggests that the technology is well-designed to serve users at all phases of their professional path, ensuring that everyone benefits from its features.

Conclusions

There are more young registered bookkeepers than older ones. The majority are female. The majority of practitioners are newly

registered, notwithstanding their years of practice. Bookkeepers in Revenue District 78 Binalbagan, classified by profile, are highly aware and highly satisfied in the Bureau of Internal Revenue's ORUS.

They have the same level of awareness and are equally satisfied of the ORUS regardless of age, sex, or years of practice.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, it was recommended to engage all staff in each division to promote taxpayer knowledge and satisfaction. A responsive workforce can be created to assist taxpayers in becoming skilled with new technology. It is crucial to thoroughly understand user experiences and identify areas of difficulty. A communication strategy can be devised to keep everyone informed by scheduling frequent webinars and seminars in each city and municipality to gauge awareness and satisfaction with the new system. A regular evaluations can be conducted to discover areas for improvement and change accordingly. Regularly analyze user behavior, gather feedback, and enhance in-app instructions to ensure the system aligns with user needs and organizational goals. A testimonial page on the intranet can be created to showcase early adopters' successes. Use various mediums, including in-depth case studies, video interviews, and written testimonies, to highlight their experiences and the system's benefits.

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